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INSTITUT FRANCAIS DE
BIOINFORMATIQUE

ACTIVITY REPORT

INSTITUT FRANÇAIS DE BIOINFORMATIQUE

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ACTIVITY REPORT 2019- 2020

FOREWORD

The year 2020 demonstrated more than ever the crucial role of data-driven life sciences for human societies. Scientists were invited to communicate in newspapers, radio and TV shows, and some concepts and terms, previously reserved to specialists, are now part of the daily vocabulary: genome, mRNA, variants, membrane proteins, cellular receptors, vaccinal strategies,...

Politicians and governments acknowledged the need for long-term support to research, and relied on scientific advisory committees to define national and international strategies. Research infrastructures provided an essential bedrock to monitor, anticipate and combat COVID-19, and to prevent future pandemics.

High expectations for bioinformatics have as well been expressed from other domains of life sciences: fundamental research, biotechnologies, agri-food, biodiversity. Integrative approaches are also emerging with the One Health concept.

As the national infrastructure of bioinformatics and the French node of the European infrastructure ELIXIR, the Institut Français de Bioinformatique (IFB, alias ELIXIR-FR) is at the crossroads of these challenges. 2019 paved the way to consolidate IFB sustainability, with a very positive evaluation of our 2018-2021 roadmap, a validation of the IFB renewal through funding by the Ministry of Science and the National Research Agency, and a strong commitment of our supporting institutions to open permanent positions.

...

FOREWORD

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In addition, IFB is leading an ambitious 16.5M project “Mutualised Digital Spaces for FAIR Life Sciences” (MUDIS4LS) funded by the national PIA3 call ESR/Equipex+ (Equipements Structurants pour la Recherche), that gathers 37 teams (IFB platforms, data centers, mesocenters and data-producing infrastructures) from 16 research organizations and 160 persons, totaling 40 FTE of involvement in the 4 work packages and 5 thematic implementation studies. This funding will lay down the basis of IFB infrastructure for our 2021-2025 roadmap, and strengthen several priority activities, e.g., FAIR data, integration of imaging, multi-omics and phenomics data, applications of IA to life sciences, deployment of certified Health Data Storage (HDS) digital spaces.

2020 was definitely marked by the worldwide sanitary crisis with the COVID-19 pandemic. Paradoxically, the global crisis did not slow down our achievement of objectives. We pursued our usual activities and attempted to keep as well as possible our missions of support, training and innovative developments, despite the inherent difficulties of remote working. Moreover, IFB was highly solicited to contribute to the national and international efforts in fighting the pandemic. At the beginning of the lockdown, we established an IFB COVID-19 task force, took part in the COVID-19 network animated by EBI and ELIXIR, and committed to lead a WP on the EMERGEN national project of genomic surveillance.

In 2020 we also handled a call to enlarge the IFB network, which now includes 21 member platforms, 8 contributing platforms and 7 associated research teams. In summary, in 2019-2020 the Institut Français de Bioinformatique consolidated its foundations to build a strong and sustainable national bioinformatics infrastructure. The achievements and activities during this period are described in this activity report. The last chapter presents a perspective on three new projects undertaken in 2021: MUDIS4LS, EMERGEN, and ABRomics.

**Claudine Médigue
and Jacques van Helden**

Co-directors of the Institut Français de Bioinformatique (IFB)

ACTIVITY REPORT 2019-2020

IFB
AT A
GLANCE

The Institut Français de Bioinformatique (IFB) is a national service infrastructure that offers the life sciences and bioinformatics communities, access to resources critical to their research, support for projects at the highest level of expertise, and the opportunity to participate in ambitious projects at the national and international level.

The IFB federates through its core team IFB-Core, a network of bioinformatics platforms affiliated to the main French research organizations. Thanks to this nationwide coverage, the IFB structures a national bioinformatics community by pooling technical and human resources and disseminating know-how.

ACTIVITY REPORT 2019-2020

IFB IMPACT

The following figures were collected in 2019 (31 PFs & teams), compared to 2020 (21 member PFs), showing a significant improvement.

Support actions to users

1892
projects
for 2019-2020

Scientific collaborations 2019-2020

Training

Outreach & publications

IFB AS THE FRENCH NODE OF ELIXIR

At the European level, IFB is the French Node of ELIXIR. ELIXIR is an intergovernmental organization that coordinates and develops life science resources across Europe so that researchers can more easily find, analyze and share data, exchange expertise, and implement best practices.

ELIXIR-FR is amongst the largest nodes of the European bioinformatics infrastructure, with a large panel of platforms, activities and services addressing a wide diversity of domains such as human health, food & agriculture, and marine diversity. Our activities encompass most of the ELIXIR platforms (compute, tools, training, interoperability). The development of our national registry of bioinformatics resources (compute & storage facilities, tools, training materials, expertise, teams) is synchronized with the corresponding ELIXIR registries (bio.tools, EDAM, TeSS) and standards (Bioschemas) in order to enable a both-ways programmatic synchronization between resources annotated in the French and ELIXIR repositories.

orphadata

Biolmage Informatics Index

*Food and Nutrition: emerging
Toxicology: emerging - co-lead*

7
**co-leads/
leads**
of ELIXIR
Communities
and Platforms

12
**Implementation
studies** funded
by ELIXIR with
a total of
350 k€

IFB 2018-2021 ROADMAP

IFB has a fundamental role in the mutualization of physical, logistics, and human resources to address users' needs, to promote technological developments, to enforce technology and scientific watch at the national and European levels (via ELIXIR), to set-up training in line with the constant evolution of the domain, and to provide user support.

The IFB work plan is organized around a "mutualized task-force" gathering various experts of different IFB platforms to optimize the sharing of knowledge and competences, the design of robust and innovative solutions, and to deploy IFB services. This synergistic federation of bioinformatics regional platforms is clearly an important added value of the IFB infrastructure relative to the sum of individual platforms - the result is more than the sum of the parts.

Significant progress has been made in the past two years, despite the current COVID-19 sanitary crisis. IFB has focused on strengthening its 2018-2021 roadmap with a dynamic group of engineers and researchers, and by working on its implementation through numerous teleconferences complemented by very rare face-to-face meetings in 2020.

All the actions of the IFB 2018-2021 roadmap target the whole community of life science researchers (wet lab biologists and bioinformaticians).

It includes :

- **Compute and Storage** services of IFB organized around the National Network of Computing Resources (NNCR), which federates 8 cloud sites and 7 cluster servers spread over 9 regional centers.
- **Software/database development and deployment** made available to user communities in various ways (Web interfaces, Web services, downloads, conda packages, containers).
- **Training**, a very important activity of the individual platforms and of the infrastructure as a whole. IFB is adopting the best practices guidelines and metrics to deliver a FAIR training aligned with open science guidances.

- Developments on **integrative bioinformatics** to address the challenging task of heterogeneous data integration (multi-omics, imaging, phenotypes) in the context of research projects in biology, environment, agronomy and health.

- **A centralized help desk** to ensure the follow-up of the requests addressed to IFB-Core, and their dispatching towards the most competent platforms depending on the nature of the request.

- **Consultancy and user support to life scientists**, a very strong component of the IFB activities (conception of a project, data management, analysis workflows, interpretation of the results) which answers an important demand for our users. The number of collaborative projects to analyze data from life scientists is around 800 a year with about one third of them leading to international publications.

ACTIVITY REPORT 2019-2020

SURVEY
OF THE NEEDS
OF OUR
COMMUNITIES

Goals of the survey

At the end of 2019, IFB conducted a survey targeting the life sciences and bioinformatics communities. The targeted researchers belonged to our main funding bodies, as well as to the data-producing national infrastructures. In total, more than **400 answers were collected**, mostly from whole teams rather than individuals. The main goal

of this survey was to orientate IFB actions towards the actual expectations of the user communities. It was intended to measure the evolution of the needs from the life sciences communities. This was achieved through a set of questions addressing several topics, of which:

- Exponential increase in storage and computing requirements
- Growing need in bioinformatics skills and competencies
- Use of specific and rapidly evolving software resources
- Access to specialized databases
- Need to control the entire processing chain to ensure the openness and reproducibility of results (Data Management Plan, workflows, software environments)

As expected, most of **the answers were given by teams or units, working either in biology or in bioinformatics**.

It gives a good base to catch a vision of bioinformatics needs for those two communities.

SURVEY OF THE NEEDS OF OUR COMMUNITIES

The main information gained is that both communities expect to see bioinformatics questions take on more and more importance. To illustrate that, we can see the huge expectations about recruitment, training and collaboration.

75% of participants wish to engage in training.

The survey shows **the lack of knowledge about “Data Management Plan”** and raises the huge necessity of spreading knowledge and training about DMP. For that purpose, IFB established two courses on data management in bioinformatics since the survey (see Training section).

The survey also highlights **the importance of training around bioinformatics competences** (data analysis, workflows, biostatistics...) and it's a point IFB improved significantly since 2019 with the creation of a University Diploma in Integrative Bioinformatics (see Training section).

Finally, the survey shows **the growing need of computing & storage infrastructures due to the increase of projects** generating a lot of data to store and the need of an increase compute capability to analyse them. This raises questions like:

- . how to deal with sensitive data (HDS)?
- . How to answer the storage problem of old projects?
- . And how to improve the computational and storage facilities?

IFB will deal with these questions in its future projects.

[>> Detailed report of the survey](#)

Skills required in units/teams

Computing and storage facilities

Current volume of active data stored by the unit

Visibility of active data storage requirements over 3 years

ACTIVITY REPORT 2019- 2020

SURVEY OF THE NEEDS OF OUR COMMUNITIES

Software resources

Use of French bioinformatics resources

Types of data analysed

Data management

Familiarity with the concept of Data Management Plan (DMP)

Artificial intelligence

Types of data for which AI methods are used

SURVEY OF THE NEEDS OF OUR COMMUNITIES

Training

Demand for training in data production technologies

Training needs in bioinformatics/biostatistics analysis

A QUICK TOUR OF IFB SERVICES

COMPUTE AND STORAGE:
THE NATIONAL NETWORK OF COMPUTING RESOURCES

SOFTWARE ENVIRONMENTS

IFB CATALOG OF FRENCH BIOINFORMATICS RESOURCES

ELIXIR-FR SERVICE DELIVERY PLAN (SDP)

INSTITUT FRANÇAIS DE BIOINFORMATIQUE

COMPUTE AND STORAGE: THE NATIONAL NETWORK OF COMPUTING RESOURCES

The National Network of Computing Resources (NNCR) federates 8 cloud sites and 7 cluster servers spread over 9 regional centers. The compute and storage services of IFB are organized around the NNCR, targeting the whole community of life science researchers. The following points highlight the main activities for this network over the past two years.

CATEGORY	INDICATOR	2019	2020
COMPUTE AND STORAGE SERVICES			
	TOTAL NUMBER OF ACTIVE USERS	7 811	9 115
	NEW USER ACCOUNTS OPENED	3 556	2 911
	ACTIVE PROJECT SPACES	7 670	6 886
SOFTWARE DEVELOPMENT AND DEPLOYMENT			
	NEW SOFTWARE TOOLS DEVELOPED	72	56
	DOWNLOADS OF SOFTWARE TOOLS	18 540	16 607
	UNIQUE USERS FOR WEB INTERFACES OF IFB RESSOURCES	302 143	423 424

IFB Core Cluster

- The IFB core cluster is managed by the NNCR task force. In 2020 it hosted 509 active user accounts on Slurm and 627 active user accounts on usegalaxy and active project spaces.
- Release of usegalaxy.fr mid-2020, a generalist instance which also hosts 2 thematic subdomains: workflow4metabolomics.usegalaxy.fr and proteore.usegalaxy.fr
- Proposal for a new service: [JupyterHub](#), that allows users to launch a dedicated JupyterLab environment running on the cluster infrastructure as a batch job. JupyterLab integrates by default Python and R kernel including all required libraries for data science, a RStudio environment, and an Unix Terminal. All users can add their own jupyter kernel.
- A new storage from DDN implementing the Lustre filesystem that fixes our main bottleneck since the IFB Core Cluster release.

COMPUTE AND STORAGE: THE NATIONAL NETWORK OF COMPUTING RESOURCES

IFB NNCR Clusters

- The IFB NNCR Cluster is composed of:
 - . HPC infrastructure
 - . 16900 vCPU
 - . 92 TB RAM
 - . 10.5 PB of storage
 - . 10 GPU cards
- A total of 7 IFB platforms have now plugged their respective clusters into the [tools gitlab repository](#), enabling the parallel installation – based on Conda and Singularity – of up to 400 scientific tools into 7 computing infrastructures.
- These platforms also mutualized human resources with 15 engineers involved in the NNCR Cluster Task Force.
- The [community support platform](#) now gathers different IFB and other communities (ie: Cluster, Galaxy, Workflow4Metabolomic).
So far, 13 expert teams have been created to help end-users on various topics: bank, software, galaxy, workflow, RNASeq, ChipSeq, among others.

Servers	Location	Compute (#CPU HT*)	Storage (#TB)	RAM (#GB)	RAM/core (#GB)	GPU (#Card)
ifb-core-cluster	Orsay (IDRIS)	4300	[2]400	20008	4,65	-
ABiMS	Roscoff	2600	2500	10600	5,50	2
GENOTOUL	Toulouse	6224	4400	36500	5,56	1
GenOuest	Rennes	1866	2300	11616	6,23	7
BiRD	Nantes	902	600	6800	6,79	-
Migale	Jouy en Josas	1016	350	7000	6,89	-
Total IFB clusters		16908	10550	92524	35,64	10

IFB NNCR Federation

- Pre-defined bioinformatics environments, available with a one-click deployment from the RAINBio catalog:
 - ▮ Domain-specific environments like genomics, (assembly, mapping, regulation, expression profiling, annotation, visualization, etc) and bioimaging (ImageJ-Fiji, Icy, OMERO).
 - ▮ Generic research environments with Rstudio server, Shiny apps and Jupyter notebooks.
 - ▮ Most configurations rely on public git repositories available in Biosphere Apps Commons.
 - ▮ Administration rights in the user's environment to tune the installation of bioinformatics tools and configurations.
- A unified portal [Biosphere](#) to deploy all bioinformatics environments on all clouds.
 - ▮ Single sign-on, with the user's academic credentials (identity federation).
- 8 cloud sites with more than 6,000 vCPU and 29 TB RAM
 - ▮ High-availability, thanks to the different sites of the cloud federation.
- Modular cloud environments
 - ▮ Single virtual machine (VM) to a bunch of VMs.
 - ▮ Usual VM: up to 64 vCPUs-250 GB RAM.
 - ▮ Big memory VM with up to 3 TB RAM.
 - ▮ HighFrequency VM : up to 3.8GHz vCPU.
 - ▮ ManyCores VM: up to 255 vCPUs in a VM
- Useful public biological reference databases are proposed.
- On-demand resources (CPU, RAM, storage) and expertise to support projects and trainings, university courses, scientific schools, workshops, hackathons.

Platform	Location	Compute (#CPU HT*)	Storage (#TB)	RAM (#GB)
IFB Core	Lyon (CC-IN2P3)	3936	408	20408
AuBI	Clermont-Ferrand	200	20	800
GenQuest	Rennes	600	350	2600
PRABI	Lyon	448	144	1500
BiRD	Nantes	512	50	2048
BIGEst	Strasbourg	200	50	1024
BILILLE	Lille	192	0	768
CBP-PSMN	Lyon	192	24	192
Total federation of clouds		6280	1046	29340

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Participation to ELIXIR Tools activities

IFB is strongly engaged in the activities of the ELIXIR Tools Platform. In ELIXIR EXCELERATE this engagement was initiated with our participation in the construction of the bio.tools registry. We have expanded our engagement through strategic resources such as Biocontainers, and the coordination of the platform itself.

. Biocontainers

ELIXIR Tools Platform is the provider of Biocontainers, a community-based repository of Docker and Singularity images for bioinformatics software. Along with a set of best practices for image development, the repository is managed by a continuous integration system that checks containers descriptors, automatically builds images and pushes them to a public repository and a backup system. It also provides security scan reports of containers, a public facing website to search, and a GA4GH compliant API for container discovery. It integrates with Bio.tools to share Biocontainers metadata.

Containers are created from two main sources, Conda recipes and Docker build recipes. IFB is one of the main contributors of this repository, working on the Docker source side (ELIXIR-DE working on the Conda side), managing the build infrastructure (hosted at EBI), injecting new tools and user support.

IFB is also involved in most work packages related to containers. Biocontainers is in production and is widely used in the community.

SOFTWARE ENVIRONMENTS

. **Bio.tools**

One of the main resources of the ELIXIR Tools Platform is **bio.tools**, a comprehensive registry of tools and data services for all domains of bioinformatics. IFB is one of the major partners in this resource, by steadily contributing through multiple actions. IFB has contributed to its development, mostly through the testing and documentation phases, but also with the development of specific features, such as the annotation of bio.tools entries with Bioschemas. The success of this resource is reflected by the growing number of resources (more than 17000) and the increasing number of users (over 1800). This continued development of bio.tools, the underlying biotoolsSchema data model, and the community-based curation mechanisms have been described in multiple publications over the last years.

. EDAM: a new ELIXIR multi-node service

EDAM is a reference domain ontology to describe the major concepts of bioinformatics in a machine-understandable way. As one of the main contributing organizations to EDAM, IFB has been participating in the development of the contents of EDAM with two new versions, 1.24 and 1.25, that were released in 2020. IFB is also currently working on a new development workflow that includes a more thorough and performant validation process. In addition to these technical developments, ELIXIR-FR has submitted EDAM in December 2020 as a joint service of ELIXIR France and ELIXIR Norway. This submission includes an ambitious roadmap to establish a new governance model and funding mechanisms that will accelerate its development, facilitate community contributions, and ensure the long term sustainability of the project.

. ELIXIR Tools ecosystem

The **ELIXIR Tools Platform** has initiated the development of the “Tools Platform Ecosystem” in 2019. This metadata exchange platform will coordinate the metadata describing software, as well as the services described in different registries, and the services maintained by the ELIXIR Tools Platform, using standards such as EDAM, Bioschemas, and biotoolsSchema. Building on top of the content aggregated and curated over the last years, it will open up the content and make it accessible beyond API calls, facilitate cross-linking and enrichment within and beyond the ELIXIR Tools Platform, and hence contributing to the FAIRness and sustainability of bioinformatics tools. In production, this platform will serve as the central tool-metadata hub for the Tools Platform resources, and provide integration with other services and communities within and beyond ELIXIR. Since 2019, ELIXIR-FR has contributed to the design and development of this ecosystem, mainly through the creation of the metadata processing bots. Although it is still currently in beta, it now stores metadata from major Tools Platform services (bio.tools, Biocontainers, OpenEBench), but also from multiple external resources such as the BiImage Informatics Index (BISE), or the Debian Med and BioConda packaging systems.

IFB CATALOG OF FRENCH BIOINFORMATICS RESOURCES

SERVICES FOR WHOM ?

Contents of the catalog

In order to ensure an optimal findability, accessibility, and visibility to the various resources and expertise available in the French bioinformatics community, IFB implemented a catalog covering databases, software tools, computing and storage resources, training sessions and materials, as well as the individual and collective expertise available, not only in the platforms affiliated with IFB, but also belonging or maintained by all French scientific organizations.

By maintaining such an exhaustive and detailed census, IFB aims at improving the individual visibility and accessibility of the various resources available, but also providing a global vision of the bioinformatics community, and guiding activities such as consulting, collaborations, project building etc.

What it will enable us to do

This catalog is built on a data model which supports an extensive description of resources, covering their scientific purpose, as well as their technical and administrative aspects, and the relationships between the different entities (e.g., this training session covers this database, this person is the author of this software tool). Noteworthy, it includes a class "service", which links the different elements underlying a specific service: computing infrastructure, software tools and/or databases, training material, teams and people ensuring the service. The catalog itself is built using the Django framework and its contents are stored in a PostgreSQL database. The contents of the database are available via a user-friendly interface on the IFB website. A programmatic access is also available, using a REST API. Finally, the web pages describing the resources will be annotated with BioSchemas markup when appropriate profiles are available.

The catalog is currently being populated with the information about IFB platforms, imported from the previous IFB website, and it will serve as the back-end for the new website (several web pages will be generated by querying the catalog API), but also for some thematic portals associated to specific IFB projects (e.g., the French section of the COVID-19 data portal, the resources of the ABRomics multi-omics platform for antibioresistance).

Synergies with the ELIXIR resources: bio.tools, TeSS, EDAM, Tools ecosystem

The maintenance and curation of the IFB catalog is performed by the owners/maintainers of the different resources, and therefore relies largely on the contribution of the French bioinformatics community. To facilitate this curation at international level and avoid duplicate registration and maintenance, the catalog will be synchronized with the different registries and resource aggregators available in ELIXIR ([bio.tools](#) for software and services, [TeSS](#) for training and training materials, [WorkflowHub](#) for workflows and [FAIRsharing](#) for databases). For instance, all tools registered in bio.tools are imported in the catalog using the bio.tools API, and the training materials and sessions registered are aggregated in TeSS using their BioSchemas-formatted description. To facilitate the interoperability within these registries, the data model of the catalog uses as much as possible annotation standards such as the EDAM ontology, to describe the resources.

ELIXIR-FR SERVICE DELIVERY PLAN (SDP)

In Autumn 2018, ELIXIR-FR launched a call for the renewal of its Service Delivery Plan (SDP). In total, 103 descriptions of services were received, essentially organized around databases and software tools, among which, 89 were proposed for the ELIXIR SDP. The submissions were evaluated by an international panel of referees and a committee, based on a set of ELIXIR-derived criteria to evaluate the impact, the compliance with ELIXIR recommendations, and the sustainability of the services.

This process led, in 2019, to the selection of 29 services to be declared in the ELIXIR-FR SDP, compared to 12 in 2016. These services are mostly found in the Plant Sciences, Microbial Biotechnology, Human Data, and Marine Metagenomics ELIXIR communities.

Of note, [Orphadata](#) has been labelled as an ELIXIR core data resource in January 2019, and the submission of the International Immunogenetics Information System (IMGT) in 2020, led to very positive feedback from ELIXIR Hub. The IMGT PIs were asked to work on the licensing of the IMGT database to fully address the Open Science criteria of an ELIXIR core data resource. ELIXIR-FR will resubmit this resource in the next ELIXIR call.

Number of ELIXIR-FR services

Access to all French services

The complete list of [ELIXIR-FR](#) services has been officially renewed in 2019 (Service Delivery Plan). In December 2020, ELIXIR-FR made a joint submission of an application for inclusion in the Norwegian and French SDP. All the services in ELIXIR-FR SDP have been submitted to bio.tools and annotated in a standardized way using EDAM.

List of services:

- on [ELIXIR website](#)
- In [bio.tools](#)

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INNOVATION:
INTEGRATIVE
BIOINFORMATICS

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A general description of the Integrative Bioinformatics axis and its pilot projects is available here:

[Integrative Bioinformatics](#).

The pilot projects crystallized collaborations between several national research infrastructures (IFB, France Génomique, MetaboHub, ProFI, FRISBI, FLI, Phenome...) and two model facilities for animals and human cohorts (PHENOMIN, BIOBANQUES).

The ProMetIS project which integrates genomics (FG), proteomics (ProFI) and metabolomics (MetaboHub) data started in June 2018. Alyssa Imbert worked on the project as a post-doc/research engineer from January 2019 to March 2021. She presented several posters and talks during the course of the project and two publications are in preparation.

An R package with the results of the projects is [now available on the IFB ELIXIR-FR GitHub repository](#). It includes nine datasets (proteomics and metabolomics analysis of liver and plasma samples from the LAT and MX2 knock-out mice), as well as the full code used for the statistical analysis and a detailed tutorial. The ProMetIS project and package are presented within the integrative bioinformatics DUBii university diploma co-organized by IFB. The manuscript describing the ProMetIS dataset "ProMetIS: deep phenotyping of mouse models by combined proteomics and metabolomics analysis" is in a revision process for publication in the Nature communication journal.

INNOVATION: INTEGRATIVE BIOINFORMATICS

The **MS2MODELS** project, which integrates proteomics (ProFI) and 3D structural (FRISBI) data, started in July 2018 and ran until December 2019. Guillaume Postic and Victor Reys worked on the project as postdocs/research engineers. Guillaume presented several posters and talks during the course of the project and first-authored two publications (Postic and al., J Proteome Res. 2020; Postic and al., Nucleic Acids Res. 2021). A web application allowing to find interaction networks from a list of proteins is [available here](#).

The **INEX-MED** project which integrates genomics (FG) and imaging (FLI) data started in October 2018. Maxime Folschette and Kirsley Chennen worked on the project as postdocs/research engineers from November 2018 to February 2019. They presented a poster and a demo at JOBIM 2019 ([available here](#)) during the course of the project. Further collaborations between IFB and France Life Imaging are on the way. The project is presented within the integrative bioinformatics DUBii university diploma co-organized by IFB.

The **PhenoMeta** project which integrates metabolomics (MetaboHub) and imaging (Phenome) data started in July 2018. Mélanie Buy and Bilal El Houdaigui worked on the project as research engineers from October 2018 to April 2020. The project led to the publication of integrated and interoperable datasets and contributed to build the FAIR Data-finder for Agronomic REsearch service ([available here](#)).

The **IntegrParkinson** project which integrates genomics (FG), metabolomics (MetaboHub) and imaging (FLI) data started in October 2018. Etienne Camenen worked on the project as a post-doc/research engineer from September 2018 to August 2020. His work was presented at JOBIM 2019 as a poster and published in 2020 ([available here](#)). He made the RGCCA R package available in **galaxy** and as a **shiny application**.

OPEN
SCIENCE

Facing the challenges of modern biology requires the analysis and sharing of increasing amounts of data.

To meet these challenges, researchers must maintain a high level of competence in their fields of research, but they also need to face new constraints:

- cope with the deluge of data generated through high-throughput methods,
- meet societal transparency expectations and foster cumulative sciences,
- efficiently leverage massively produced data to accelerate scientific discovery.

Open Science provides answers to all of these points through the unhindered dissemination of research publications, data, computational tools, and through the construction of an ecosystem in which science is more cumulative, more strongly data-driven, more transparent, and faster. It also has an ethical/deontological component by promoting replicability and reproducibility of results, strengthening the argument for evidence of scientific results. In the affirmation of its values, IFB proactively contributes to this movement through the development of Life Science data and compute infrastructures and the setting up of training courses.

OPEN SCIENCE

FAIR-checker

FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles are nowadays the cornerstone to accelerate the development of reusable (life-science) digital resources.

However, as principles,

they do not recommend technological choices.

The question is: how to move from human-oriented checklists, to computational tools facilitating their adoption and implementation for resource developers and providers?

Technical tips are needed to better automate and progress in the FAIRification of Bioinformatics resources.

IFB is actively developing [FAIR-checker](#), a web interface aimed at monitoring progress in FAIRification by automated testing and reporting. This tool has been presented as a short talk during the ELIXIR All-Hands 2020 meeting. This tool is greatly supported by the [FAIR Maturity Evaluation Service APIs](#).

It proposes new metrics, leveraging semantic web technologies (embedded RDF, SPARQL queries, SHACL constraints) to evaluate web resource metadata. In addition, FAIR-checker proposes a set of recommendations for developers to better cope with each of the FAIR principles. The FAIR-checker project has been registered in the [FAIRAssist catalog](#) of the well-established [FAIRsharing](#) resource. In our future developments, we aim at proposing quality-oriented tests to evaluate annotations against metadata community profiles specifying minimal, recommended, and optional annotations.

The following figure shows a screenshot of FAIR-checker. It shows how a bioinformatics tool, registered on bio.tools, performs in terms of FAIR principles.

How FAIR is my resource ?

Enter resource identifier (URL/DOI)

<https://bio.tools/jaspar>

[Test all metrics](#)

Examples ▾

[Dataset Databases](#) [Workflow](#) [Publication Databases](#) [Dataset](#) [Tool](#)

Progress

[Clean results](#)

Radar chart of metrics completion

List of metrics with details and results

Principle	Name	Description	Time	Comment	Recommendation	Score	Result	Test
F1	Unique Identifier		0:00:02			1	Success	Check
F1	Identifier Persistence		0:00:02			0	Failure	Check
F1	Data Identifier Persistence		0:00:05			0	Failure	Check

FAIR-checker. Computational evaluation and reporting on the compliance of the bio.tools/jaspar resource with FAIR principles.

OPEN SCIENCE

Bioschemas

Bioschemas is a large community effort aiming at reusing and extending [Schema.org](https://schema.org) specifications to enhance the findability of web resources through semantic annotations (metadata). ELIXIR-FR participates in the Bioschemas Strategic Implementation Study, and in the frame of the Plant use case, is currently deploying a Bioschemas markup through the FAIDARE indexing and search engine for plant genotyping and phenotyping.

Through our involvement in both the ELIXIR Tools and Interoperability platforms, we automated the generation of Bioschemas semantic annotations in Bio.Tools.

This results in 17.000+ annotated bioinformatics tools with Bioschemas markup. We also developed a web crawler which compiles a complete [Bioschemas dataset](#) that feeds the ELIXIR Tools Ecosystem. This full dataset can then be combined with the EDAM ontology.

It results in a web queryable knowledge base for bioinformatics tools, as shown in [10.3233/SW-200374](https://doi.org/10.3233/SW-200374).

Our activities, both on the generic FAIR computational evaluation (FAIR-checker) as well as on the evolution and the deployment of the Bioschemas Tools specification led us to recently join the Bioschemas Steering Council.

Biolmage Informatics Index (BISE), an ELIXIR Interoperability Resource (RIR)

The BISE platform developed by the Network of European Bio-image Analysts (NEUBIAS COST network), tries to match given image analysis problems with relevant bioimaging tools. IFB is involved in this project mostly through the EDAM ontology that allows collaboratively design and development of the EDAM BioImaging Ontology, as well as tools to automatically update BISE for each new release of the ontology. This contribution played a major role in the acceptance of BISE as a Recommended Interoperability Resource (RIR) by the ELIXIR Interoperability Platform.

Managing data for life sciences

Data management has become a cornerstone issue for IFB. Several IFB projects aim at developing technical solutions and engaging communities in the adoption of data management practices. Some of our ongoing actions are highlighted below. IFB has also launched a new training on data management to tackle this (see section Training).

- Harmonization of data management approaches between national infrastructures

National research infrastructures are encouraged to develop infrastructure-specific **Data Management Plan (DMPs)**, which are complementary to the project DMPs. In the context of IFB action “mutualization of resources between national infrastructures”, a DMP model is being developed for the French bio imagery community in collaboration with France Bio Imaging (FBI) and the French node of the European Marine Biological Resource Centre (EMBRC-FR). This model is currently in beta-testing.

- **maDMP4LS**: coupling DMPWs to the Compute & Storage access

This project (machine actionable DMP for Life Sciences) funded by ANR (19-DATA-0017-01), aims to make the DMP-OPIDoR tool interoperable with the user and project management tools of IFB. To achieve this, a new machine-actionable version of DMP is under development (ma-OPIDoR), using the RDA (Research Data Alliance) model. On the IFB side, new features are added to configuration and data management applications in order to make them interoperable with ma-OPIDoR.

ACTIVITY REPORT 2019- 2020

HIGHLIGHTS: INTERNATIONAL SYNERGIES

IFB has developed strong international synergies, as part of its role as the French node of ELIXIR,

these include:

- Develop and leverage the ecosystem of bioinformatic tools for the French life-science research community. In 2019, IFB has done a lot of groundwork that avoids an unnecessary double maintenance of catalogs while streaming the resources to the French community (see section IFB catalog), and to better coordinate its Galaxy community and computing resources.
- Enhance the impact of capacity building events and training through active contributions to: hackathons, train-the-trainers training sessions, training in collaboration with other nodes addressing gaps in (Machine learning, data management in epitranscriptomics, etc.).

IFB is also promoting ELIXIR activities aiming at ensuring that the services delivered meet the needs of domain specific communities.

For that purpose, ELIXIR-FR contributes to the development of prioritized roadmaps. In 2019-2020, three of such roadmaps were published: **hCNV**, **3D-Bioinfo**, **IDPs**. As well as to common coordination and developments activities supported by various means: ELIXIR funded projects (in 2019-2020, 5 newly funded with ELIXIR-FR as coordinator or partner); the yearly European BioHackathon that allows invitations of experts outside of ELIXIR; other projects funded at the national or EC level. This allows ELIXIR-FR and its French partners to give more impact to its own portfolio of services and to facilitate the adoption of services maintained by other nodes.

HIGHLIGHTS: INTERNATIONAL SYNERGIES

Some examples relevant to the 2019-2020 period are given below:

- The **human Copy Number Variation (hCNV) community** is perhaps a recent and very good example of the implementation of the strategy described before. It is led by ELIXIR-FR since 2019. The roadmap of the community was released in 2020 ([hCNV](#)). Following its priorities, the group started to implement a benchmarking infrastructure based on Galaxy environment and conda containers to improve CNV detection pipelines. In parallel, a collection of 245 CNV detection tools were generated. Half of the tools (109) are now accessible in a specific [bio.tools domain](#). Additionally, the hCNV community has been active in the field of interoperability and data discovery by contributing to the definition of BEACON specifications for CNV and Structural Variants (participation to the Beacon Scout team for CNV and SV), GA4GH task force on future of VCF (Variant Call Format File) and implementers of Beacon V2 specifications on national CNV resources ([progenetix](#) and [Banco](#)). These activities were coordinated using an ELIXIR funded project (first implementation study of the hCNV) European Biohackathon 2019 and 2020, as well as [ELIXIR-FR curatathon](#) held in Paris 2020. The work planned within the community will be pursued thanks to 2 ELIXIR implementations studies that have been granted to the community running from 2021 to 2023.

- The **Plant Sciences community** has been co-led by ELIXIR-FR since 2018. A software developed by ELIXIR-FR and based on a global standard API, the Breeding API, has been chosen to set up the data portal of the ELIXIR Plant Sciences community: [the FAIDARE portal](#). The information systems that can be searched through FAIDARE are compliant with several international standards to which the ELIXIR Plant Sciences community as a whole contributed. The development of FAIDARE has been funded by ELIXIR (ELIXIR-EXCELERATE), and by the french nodes of ELIXIR and EMPHASIS. The ELIXIR nodes contributing to the Plant Sciences community have been very powerful in streaming their service and expertise portfolio into several projects funded by EC calls starting in 2020 and dedicated to the characterization of genetic resources ([e.g. AGENT Project](#) for ELIXIR-FR).

- Since mid-2020 IFB has operated a [national Galaxy instance](#), which joins the [usegalaxy community](#). ELIXIR-FR co-led the **ELIXIR Galaxy community** from 2017 to 2020.

- ELIXIR-FR is also engaged in addressing the needs of the marine community by actively participating in the **ELIXIR Marine Metagenomic community**. Supported by large-scale sampling projects, such as the TARA projects and the development of marine models within the EMBC project, the experience acquired within this community in the development of reference databases: the Marine Atlas of Tara Oceans Unigenes ([MATOU](#)), the Ocean Microbial Reference Gene catalog ([OMRGC](#)) and the Marine Eukaryotes Transcriptomes database ([METDB](#)), of specific data models (aggregating taxonomic, genomic and environmental metadata), the deployment of tools and infrastructures for the benefit of the analysis of marine environmental data, will now be promoted to other environmental biomes as terrestrial, lacustrine, and anthropized environments.

HIGHLIGHTS: INTERNATIONAL SYNERGIES

Finally, IFB is a partner of projects funded by the European Commission (EC) and coordinated by ELIXIR Hub aiming at improving the services delivered overall by the nodes of ELIXIR, their capacity, their coordination, and their impact. Two projects were submitted in 2019 and started in 2020: ELIXIR-CONVERGE and BIMG. Both projects linked directly to French national projects.

- **ELIXIR-CONVERGE** aims at establishing a transnational service supporting the FAIR compliant data management plans of the life sciences research community. IFB is involved in several work packages of the project: expert network, training, research data management toolkit, use cases, and demonstrators. ELIXIR-CONVERGE is an opportunity to (i) develop connected national and international frameworks for data management and (ii) more specifically, to connect the French efforts to develop a COVID-19 data portal with the European COVID-19 data portal supported by ELIXIR.

■ Regarding the first point, ELIXIR-FR contributes to the content of the **ELIXIR RDMkit**, which is a repository of guidelines for FAIR compliant data management and a gateway to other supporting resources such as bio.tools, TESS, FAIRsharing (and in preparation the FAIR Cookbook, DSW). ELIXIR-CONVERGE allows to improve the service developed by ELIXIR-FR in connection with the French national projects, maDMP and MUDIS4LS starting in 2021.

■ In relation to the COVID-19 crisis, the funding of CONVERGE has doubled and the number of partners has increased for the implementation of three new work packages, all dedicated to human data. The last one, starting in 2021, is dedicated to the surveillance of COVID variants, linking directly with the French national project EMERGEN, also officially starting in 2021 with the same objective at the national level, EMERGEN (see section: Going forward 2021-2025).

- **B1MG** is an opportunity to network and to develop the capacity at the European level to give access to human genomic and clinical data. ELIXIR-FR is responsible for the organization of a workshop on how to make interoperable, the legal and technical infrastructures for such data. It is an opportunity to better connect internally as well with the France Medecine Génomique plan at national level.

ACTIVITY REPORT 2019-2020

HIGHLIGHTS: BIOINFORMATICS FOR HEALTH

HCNV

EXPERTISE ON HETEROGENEITY
OF TUMORS & ECOSYSTEM (HTE)

COVID-19 ACTIONS

Since 2019-2020, IFB has been involved in a growing number of activities related to health, at the national and international level. This includes IFB participation in research projects, the deployment of bioinformatics services enabling to combine sequencing data with health data, an expertise on the FAIRness of data generated by health-related projects, and the initiation of a new ELIXIR community focused on human copy number variations. ELIXIR-FR is also contributing to research community driven projects in collaboration with several ELIXIR nodes and ELIXIR Hub: in the bioinformatics for health domain, current on-going projects include [EJP-RD](#) (European Join program on rare diseases) and [H2020 EUCANCAN](#), which aims at aligning and interconnecting existing European and Canadian infrastructures for the analysis and management of genomic oncology data. Moreover, IFB is also involved in a user case of the H2020 [EOSC-life](#) project dedicated to health data.

In 2020, IFB has strengthened its collaboration with the [Plan France Médecine Génomique 2025](#) (PFMG2025), and an active contribution of the IFB platforms to support life and health scientists in the fight against the COVID-19 pandemic. This trend has even been reinforced by 2021, with a strong involvement of IFB in the EMERGEN national plan of genomic surveillance for COVID-19 and other infectious emerging diseases. Additionally, IFB faces an increasing demand of users to dispose of a computing and storage infrastructure certified for Health Data Storage (HDS) according to the 2017 French regulations. This demand is currently being addressed in the IFB 2021-2025 road map, with the deployment of the [MUDIS4LS project](#).

Rather than enumerating all the new health-related activities, the following pages show a few illustrative examples.

HIGHLIGHTS: BIOINFORMATICS FOR HEALTH

hCNV

ELIXIR-FR is leading the [ELIXIR human Copy Number Variation](#) community, which has been officially approved in June 2018. Since then, the hCNV community has been particularly active with multiple actions undertaken in this context, specifically:

- A one-day satellite meeting of the 2018 ESHG (European Society of Human Genetics) on CNV was organized with the Human Genome Variation Society in Goteborg (Sweden).
- A funded implementation study encompassing more than 11 ELIXIR nodes (2018-2021).
- Project proposals at the European BioHackathon in 2019 and 2020 on Beacon adaptation to CNVs, and for the containerisation of CNV detection tools to set up a Benchmarking infrastructure based on Galaxy and OpenEbench.
- A list of 245 CNVs detection tools for CGHarray and high throughput sequencing.
- Acceptance of two novel Implementation studies (2021-2024).
- Participation in various ELIXIR community and platform activities (Tools Platform (bio.tools), SIS biocontainers, ELIXIR Beacon, Rare Diseases services collection).
- Participation in EOSC-Pillar activity (WP led by Inserm-IFB), CNV detection workflow as a use case.

Expertise on Heterogeneity of Tumors & Ecosystem (HTE)

The HTE Program (Heterogeneity of Tumors & Ecosystem) is organized by ITMO Cancer, in collaboration with ITMO BCDE (Cell Biology, Development and Evolution) and ITMO Technologies for Health of the National Alliance for Life Sciences and Health (AVIESAN) with the National Cancer Institute (INCA) and Inserm within the framework of the Cancer Plan. The operational management of this program is entrusted to Inserm. Six networks of 39 multidisciplinary teams are involved in the HTE Program.

In September 2019, ITMO Cancer mandated the IFB to evaluate a dedicated infrastructure built for the HTE program. Based on this solicitation, a group of IFB members was set up to work on the expertise proposal. In February 2020, a presentation of the possible assets of the HTE platform was given to the steering committee of the HTE program. Few weeks later the expertise proposal was accepted by the steering committee. The expert group organized a dedicated platform presentation meeting in December 2020, between the HTE consortium representatives and IFB members. The current HTE platform evaluation proposal will focus on the study of the adequacy between the developed infrastructure and users' needs, as well as a set of services related to data usability, data management and recommendations in regards to processing sensitive data (CNIL/RGPD).

Since the acceptance of the PIA3 Equipex+ grant, MUDIS4LS, IFB is no longer considering the HTE infrastructure as an external project to evaluate, but rather as a potential demonstrator of the feasibility of a certified health data hosting <HDS> infrastructure, which is the ambition of the collaborative work between CINES, Inserm and IFB that is being developed under the Implementation Study number 3 of the MUDIS4LS project. Ideally, this joint pilot will help to evaluate the feasibility and benefits of a migration to IFB.

ACTIVITY REPORT 2019-2020

HIGHLIGHTS: BIOINFORMATICS FOR HEALTH

COVID-19 actions

In April 2020, IFB spontaneously launched a task force <IFB vs COVID-19> to support the research teams involved in fighting the pandemic. By drawing on its expertise in bioinformatics analysis, database development, statistics, and software development, the task force undertook a series of actions to support research against COVID-19. A few examples illustrate their diversity:

. IFB vs COVID-19 Task force

- Access to IFB infrastructure for computing-intensive tasks (e.g., molecular docking to identify ligands potentially useful to target SARS-CoV-2 proteins);
- Development of a SARS-CoV-2 section in the [VirHostNet](#) database;
- Hosting of Web tools developed by French researchers in different fields: epidemiology ([COVIDici](#), [Rt2en](#)), psychology ([COVIDistress](#)), comparative genomics ([PIPprofileR](#));
- [Support to biologists](#) to deploy and use their tools on a cluster facility;
- Statistical support for a [drug repositioning study](#);
- Implementation of [COVIDscan](#), a database to help physicians curating thoracic scans;
- Collaboration with virologists, evolutionary biologists, system biologists, and structural biologists to trace SARS-CoV-2 origins in genomic sequences ([DOI](#) and [DOI](#)).

. COVID-19 Data Platform

ELIXIR-FR is the French node of the [COVID-19 Data Portal](#) animated by the European Bioinformatics Institute and the ELIXIR infrastructure. Since July 2020, IFB has actively participated in the monthly teleconferences of node coordinators. Our contribution to the COVID-19 data platform will combine the results of the <IFB vs COVID-19> task force and the outcome of EMERGEN. These contributions will be displayed through a French COVID-19 portal, which will integrate information from various sources (catalog of French bioinformatics resources, gathering metadata from the different international repositories) and display them in a user-friendly way. The French COVID-19 portal will also be queryable via an API, thereby facilitating its federation with the other ELIXIR nodes within the European COVID-19 data portal.

TRAINING

EBAIL:
AVIESAN - IFB - INSERM SCHOOL OF BIOINFORMATICS
FOR NGS DATA ANALYSIS

DUBII:
UNIVERSITY DIPLOMA IN INTEGRATIVE BIOINFORMATICS

SHINY:
POTENTIATING BIOINFORMATICIANS
TO DEPLOY R APPLICATIONS

FAIR PRINCIPLES APPLIED TO BIOINFORMATICS
AND OMICS DATASETS

IFB sets up a wide diversity of training events and formats to enhance bioinformatics skills at the national level. The training activities are also articulated with similar actions developed at the European scale, as in the ELIXIR Training Platform.

. Who do we target?

IFB training activities are targeting both bioinformaticians and biologists, researchers, engineers, students, teachers, and cover national and international audiences.

. What are the expectations of our communities?

The **IFB 2019 national survey** highlighted important bioinformatics training needs in almost all teams and units. The most demanded skills are:

- NGS analysis (RNA-seq, Single-cell, Long reads, ChIP-Seq, Variants ,...) and other omics data analysis (proteomics, metabolomics, interactomics, phenomics, ..), with a recent emerging demand regarding biomedical image analysis;
- Biostatistics and data science: basic and advanced statistical analysis, R language, machine learning, AI and network inference or analysis;
- Bioinformatics: cluster usage, Unix environment and programming skills (workflow development, Python language,...), and the recent field of integrative bioinformatics.

The survey also indicates that several teams are still not very familiar with Data Management Plans (DMPs) and new training courses on the development of DMP represent an area of opportunity. With respect to training format, although short training courses (1-3 days) are clearly well suited to the availability of researchers, a one-week long immersion training is often preferred, together with training allowing to analyze data sets coming from the attendees ("Bring your Own Data").

. What do we do?

- The IFB training team works in close interaction with the task force of the IFB NNCR core cluster and with other workgroups to meet user needs and promote usage of new services. This includes the development of shared storage spaces for different groups formed during a training event: trainer team, trainers-to-trainees (demo data), trainees (project-spaces), trainee-tutors for the Bring-Your-Own-Data projects.
- We developed an eLearning material for IFB training and new users of the IFB infrastructure.

EBAii: **Aviesan-IFB-Inserm School of Bioinformatics for NGS data analysis**

The yearly Ecole de Bioinformatique Aviesan - IFB - Inserm (**EBAii**) was launched in 2013 to address an urgent need to develop bioinformatics skills inside the French teams whose projects involve Next-Generation Sequencing data (NGS). This school is addressed to biologists with no prior skills in bioinformatics, but who crucially need to acquire autonomy to handle the NGS data produced by their own research. The school lasts for a full week, and is hosted by the IFB platform ABIMS at Roscoff. The geographic isolation contributes to developing an exceptional climate of intense work and human interactions. Besides its constant and high success, the EBAii school has been the occasion to promote innovative teaching practices in our community such as BYOD and customized tutoring. It has also played a key role to structure interactions between IFB regional platforms: sharing of teaching materials and good practices, early stages of the NNCR creation, federation of a **network of experts**, adoption of new technologies in the IFB infrastructure (Conda, Singularity).

DUBii: **University Diploma in Integrative Bioinformatics**

A level-graduate training in bioinformatics for life scientists (**DUBii**) was set up in partnership with Université de Paris, training 54 biologists and health professionals during the past 3 years. The training targets life-science professionals and physicians with a first experience in bioinformatics (self-training, bioanalysis or bioinformatics development) aiming to become bioinformaticians. The course contents were designed in close partnership with the NNCR task force, members of the IFB working groups (DMP, interoperability), faculty of Université de Paris and bioinformatics, IFB platforms, as well as research teams. The diploma was the opportunity to adopt several pedagogical innovations, regarding both content (integrative bioinformatics module, DMP adoption) and modalities (tutored project on an IFB platform, graduation character, strengthen link between the IFB infrastructure and university training).

Shiny: **Potentiating bioinformaticians to deploy R applications**

In partnership with the Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics (SIB), a new 3-days training has been designed with the purpose of leveraging bioinformaticians and biostatisticians skills to the Shiny technology. Two editions of this training have been launched in 2019 at the Institut Pasteur in Paris.

ACTIVITY REPORT 2019-2020

TRAINING

FAIR principles applied to bioinformatics and omics datasets

Two new courses have been launched in 2020 on FAIR principles applied to bioinformatics and omics datasets:

1. The **FAIR bioinfo training**, which aims to make bioinformatics analyses more reproducible by implementation of the FAIR principles in a bioinformatics analysis or development project.
2. The **FAIR data training**, which is dedicated to the fundamental aspects of Open Data, including legal aspects, practical DMP sessions, and metadata issues in the context of omics data and bioinformatics.

All new courses are open primarily to bioinformaticians from IFB platforms who are likely to become future trainers in regional platforms. The program foresees an extra optional day for IFB trainers to work on training materials. A network of trainers was gathered across regional platforms to promote new and good practices for IFB trainers: tutorship, shared training materials, make training materials FAIR, feedback mechanisms (through satisfaction surveys), and consistent description of training material and events.

• At the European level

I In February 2020, a **<Train the Trainers> event** was co-organized with the Italian ELIXIR node in Paris for two days. Further, in October 2020, a **training on Data Management and Data Stewardship** was organized with the Luxembourg ELIXIR node. This training was designed to be run for four half-days in virtual mode. More than forty people applied to the training in less than forty-eight hours.

I **ELIXIR-FR hosted the ELIXIR BioHackathon Europe 2018 in Paris.** Following the great success of the event, ELIXIR Hub solicited ELIXIR-FR to host it again in 2019. In 2020, the event ran in virtual mode and ELIXIR-F participated in the project "Design of a modular learning path (curriculum) in Data Stewardship, Management and Analysis for the Life Sciences".

I In October 2020, **TeSS (Training eSupport System)** launched a **TeSS club to build an open TeSS development community.** One particularly important aspect is the unification in the way training events are collected by TeSS from other ELIXIR nodes. Bioschemas will work as the markup standard to be adopted by other ELIXIR nodes. As Bioschemas is already being used to markup other ELIXIR-FR training events, we already started to exchange with the TeSS developer, to become beta-testers of their website scraper as soon as it is ready. Later on, ELIXIR-FR will co-lead an action aiming at promoting the adoption of Bioschemas by all ELIXIR nodes.

ACTIVITY REPORT 2019- 2020

COMMUNICATION AND INTERACTION WITH INDUSTRY

COMMUNICATION

ANALYSIS OF THE COMMUNICATION TARGETS

WEBSITE

IFB MONTHLY NEWSLETTER

INTERACTION WITH INDUSTRY

A network diagram consisting of blue dots connected by thin blue lines, forming a complex web of interconnected nodes and edges. It is located at the top right of the page.

Communication

Communication is a major strategic priority for IFB, complementary to other strategies such as the display of IFB services, the links with various users, the valorization and the implementation of new services.

The global objectives of the IFB communication strategy include:

- To provide a clear message to different users on what is IFB, its main missions, and what could be expected from IFB.
- To ensure communication coherence between our partners.
- To demonstrate progress in line with our different objectives.
- To facilitate further engagement with new partners and new users.

Analysis of communication targets

IFB has intensively worked in the past year to identify the stakeholders that are key in implementing its missions and goals.

- Researchers in life sciences and the biomedical domain;
- Bioinformaticians, first at the national level (SFBI) but also at the international level (EBI, SBI);
- IFB members (i.e., all the bioinformatics platforms);
- Authorities and research organisms;
- Industry;
- Scientific collaborators: research infrastructures (France-Génomique, MetaboHUB, Profi, etc.);
- European network (ELIXIR) and other international initiatives (Galaxy, Goblet, Bioshema).

All these targeted IFB users should perceive the value of IFB. Each communication channel has specific features, function, content type, and style. Our communication strategy relies on a careful adequacy between channels, objectives, and target audiences.

COMMUNICATION AND INTERACTION WITH INDUSTRY

Website

During 2020, IFB has worked on redesigning its website to reflect its evolution in the past few years. With new projects at the door and a new roadmap, the [new IFB website](#) clarifies the IFB governance, as well as the services provided to the general public, always with an editorial approach in mind. All the content has been reviewed and revised to reflect the most up to date orientations.

IFB monthly Newsletter

Since June 2020, IFB has set up a [monthly newsletter](#) for its members and user communities, which comprises over 500 recipients. Each month, the communication team decides on the content of the newsletter and brings together different types of information:

- A thematic editorial entrusted each time to one or more IFB members
- Recent highlights and activities in IFB
- ELIXIR projects and European initiatives
- Information about national and international events
- Job vacancies
- Training & outreach
- Scientific publications

IFB INSTITUT FRANÇAIS DE BIOINFORMATIQUE

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L'IFB recrute

Bienvenue à l'Institut Français de Bioinformatique

L'IFB est l'Infrastructure nationale de bioinformatique qui assure un support, déploie des services, organise des formations et réalise des développements innovants pour les communautés des sciences du vivant.

L'Institut Français de Bioinformatique met en place une collecte des besoins en matière d'informatique et d'analyse de données pour affronter la crise sanitaire COVID-19 et offre l'appui de ses ressources humaines et informatiques pour épauler les équipes directement impliquées.

COVID-19

En savoir +

Calcul & Stockage
Clusters • Cloud
National Network of Computing Resources (NNCR)

EN SAVOIR +

Accompagnement
Projets de recherche • Communautés • Guichet d'orientation

EN SAVOIR +

Formation
Formation professionnelle & initiale

EN SAVOIR +

Innovation
Bioinformatique intégrative

EN SAVOIR +

ELIXIR-FR
Noeud français du réseau européen d'infrastructures bioinformatiques

EN SAVOIR +

Catalogue de ressources
Outils, données, expertises, services en bioinformatique

EN SAVOIR +

Actualités
Newsletter • Réseaux sociaux

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Roadmap
Feuille de route • KPI

EN SAVOIR +

cea CNRS INRAE Inserm INVESTISSEMENTS D'AVENIR

IFB INSTITUT FRANÇAIS DE BIOINFORMATIQUE

NEWSLETTER IFB brief

Institut Français de Bioinformatique news

COMMUNICATION AND INTERACTION WITH INDUSTRY

Industry approach

IFB interaction with industry in the past years has been relatively widespread among IFB partners at national and international levels, as noted by the SAB in 2018. The complexity of IFB basic structure – a federation of bioinformatics platforms belonging to different research institutions – has played a limiting role for a proper landscaping of industrial collaborations.

IFB has oriented its efforts in the past year in building a catalog of French resources that provides access to IFB's platform expertise and resources in bioinformatics. This catalog represents a first step in ensuring the visibility of the IFB network for its potential academic and industrial partners.

IFB aims to be a major player in providing services to industry in the biotech, pharmaceutical, renewable energy, agri-food and IT sectors. The draft of an industry strategy is in preparation phase, with a work plan that outlines the IFBs positioning within the national and European research and innovation landscape.

The plan identifies **four axes of strategic development** (see figure):

- (1) the definition of a portfolio of IFB-Core only services to be offered to industrial partners under a previously approved financial model;
- (2) IFB to act as the liaison between industry potential collaborators and its member platforms, to ensure continuous engagement;
- (3) Reinforce the link between IFB, ELIXIR, and other international institutions, through the participation in international events, industry collaborations between ELIXIR nodes and European projects;
- and (4) Strengthen the engagement with French government institutions to advocate for IFB objectives in the longer term.

In the short term, a revision of the members of the Industry Advisory Committee (IAC) and the industry working group is foreseen to cope with ongoing requests. The finalization of the strategy should pave the way to increase the IFB interaction with industry.

Following this line, ELIXIR-France and ELIXIR-Belgium have engaged recently in the organization of the ELIXIR Innovation & SME Forum: [Data-driven innovation in the agritech sector](#), where IFB contributed with the participation of Anne-Françoise Adam-Blondon (Deputy Head of Node, ELIXIR-FR) and Cyril Pommier (co-leader of the [ELIXIR Plant Sciences community](#) and PI of the ELIXIR plant portal for the integration of phenotyping and genotyping data).

HIGHLIGHTS ON IFB PLATFORMS

ABiMS

Scientific Lead: Erwan Corre
Technical Lead : Gildas Le Corguillé
Research Institute: CNRS INEE
Unit/Laboratory: FR2424
City: Roscoff
Region : Bretagne
Website: abims.sb-roscoff.fr

Highlights:

- **Launch of the ANR Copilot CTS project for observation data:** Evaluation of the CTS certification of the Roscoff CDS in the framework of the [ANR copilot project](#): Pole Ocean certification.
- **Development of the Phaeoexplorer data portal:** The “France Genomique” [Phaeoexplorer](#) project aims to explore the biological complexity of brown algae through the sequencing of more than 50 genomes and transcriptomes. A [web portal](#) has been developed based on a GMOD database (Chado, JBrowse, Tripal, Galaxy).
- **Rebuilding the HPC infrastructure:** Since mid-2020, ABiMS can provide a new SLURM Cluster fully managed by modern DevOps processes (Ansible, GitLab-CI), and aligned on the IFB Core Cluster. In addition, the scientific tools and R packages are installed from the IFB GitLab repositories.
- **Co-responsibility of the IFB Core Cluster.** Since January 2019, ABiMS is strongly involved in the responsibility of the IFB Core Cluster and has the co-leadership of the [IFB Core Cluster](#).
- **Lead of the national Galaxy instance usegalaxy.fr.** This central mutualized instance hosted by the IFB Core Cluster has been in production since mid-2020.

ARTbio

Scientific Lead: Christophe Antoniewski
Technical Lead: Naira Naouar
Research Institute: Sorbonne Université
Unit/Laboratory: FR3631
City: Paris
Region: Ile-de-France
Website: www.artbio.fr

Highlights:

- **IFB COVID Task Force.** Active participation in the COVID Task Force for the coordination of efforts in the national COVID data collection.
- **Start of the Doremy clinical and genomic database project of the [CONNECT-AML Consortium](#).** ARTbio is in charge of setting up the genomic database of Acute Myeloid Leukemia of children and young adults and interfacing it with the clinical database at the Saint-Louis Hospital developed by Sylvie Chevret’s URC.
- **Start of a 1 Petabytes storage server :** project (summer 2021) implemented at Sorbonne Université. Open access but conditioned to the submission of a data management plan.

ACTIVITY REPORT 2019-2020

ATGC

Scientific Lead: Eric Rivals
& Stéphane Guindon
Technical Lead: Vincent Lefort
Research Institute: CNRS INS2I
Unit/Laboratory: UMR 5506
City: Montpellier
Region: Occitanie
Website: atgc-montpellier.fr

Highlights:

- Used by biologists for more than fifteen years, the **PhyML software**, created and maintained by Stéphane Guindon of the LIRMM (ATGC platform) is part of the arsenal of tools available to better understand and combat the SARS-CoV-2 coronavirus, responsible for the COVID-19 epidemic.
- **PEWO framework** hosts a new phylogenetic placement tool ([cf. IFB Newsletter n°5](#))

AuBi

Scientific Lead: Pierre Peyret
Technical Lead: Antoine Mahul
& Nadia Goué
Research Institute: Université d'Auvergne
Unit/Laboratory: UMR454
City: Clermont-Ferrand
Region: Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes
Website: mesocentre.uca.fr/projets-associes/plateforme-aubi

Highlights:

- **Integration of openstack resources into the IFB Cloud**
Mutualisation of UCA Mesocentre's cloud resources (OSCAR) in the IFB Cloud Federation.
- **Implementation of an OMERO server** to store images and associated metadata coming from microscopy and medical fields. This project was initiated by the GreD laboratory through the INDEPTH COST Action.
- **Contribution to Galaxy Training Network (GTN)** and involvement in teaching (Master in Bioinformatics UCA) and training hosting (DU Integrative Bioinformatics)
- **Several publications from collaborative studies:**
 - De Oliveira, R., Rimbart, H., Balfourier, F., Kitt, J., Dynomant, E., Vrána, J., Doležel, J., Cattonaro, F., Paux, E., Choulet, F. Structural Variations Affecting Genes and Transposable Elements of Chromosome 3B in Wheats. **Frontiers in Genetics** 2020 11, 891. [DOI: 10.3389/fgene.2020.00891](https://doi.org/10.3389/fgene.2020.00891)
 - Jensen S, Brasset E, Parey E, Roest Crollius H, Sharakhov IV, Vaury C. Conserved Small Nucleotide Elements at the Origin of Concerted piRNA Biogenesis from Genes and lncRNAs. **Cells** 2020 9(6) [DOI: 10.3390/cells9061491](https://doi.org/10.3390/cells9061491)
 - Robin Mom, Beatriz Muries, Pierrick Benoit, Julien Robert-Paganin, Stéphane Réty, Jean-stéphane Venisse, Agílio Pádua, Philippe Label, Daniel Auguin Voltage-gating of aquaporins, a putative conserved safety mechanism during ionic stresses. **FEBS Letters** 2020 12 [DOI: 10.1002/1873-3468.13944](https://doi.org/10.1002/1873-3468.13944)
 - Amato, P., Besaury, L., Joly, M., Penaud, B., Deguillaume, L., and Delort A.M. Metatranscriptomic exploration of microbial functioning in clouds. **Scientific Reports** 2019 9:4383. [DOI: 10.1038/s41598-019-41032-4](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-41032-4)

HIGHLIGHTS ON IFB PLATFORMS

BIGEST-BISTRO

Scientific Lead: Julie Thompson
Technical Lead : Valérie Cognat
Research Institute: CNRS IN21
Unit/Laboratory: UMR7357
City: Strasbourg
Region: Grand Est
Website: bigest.unistra.fr

Highlights:

- The Bistro platform has undergone a significant reorganization, a change that we wanted to highlight by a name change to BiGEst. **BiGEst is now the bioinformatics platform of the University of Strasbourg**, and regroups the services of the different associated laboratories in the local region. We are currently working to create a GIS (Groupement d'Intérêt Scientifique).
- **The platform is coordinating the OpenLink project**, which aims to create a bridge between data management tools by applying FAIR principles. This project aims to create a web application that allows researchers to link their various work tools in order to adopt a transversal vision of their data for each project while facilitating the transfer of information from one tool to another.
- An article describing the latest **update to the Ortholnspector ortholog database** was published in Nucleic Acids Research. With this update, Ortholnspector is one of the largest ortholog resources in terms of organism coverage.
- **The ProLine web server**: an efficient and user-friendly software suite for large-scale proteomics was described in an article [published in Bioinformatics](#).

bilille

Scientific Lead: Guillemette Marot
Technical Lead : Pierre Pericard
& Jimmy Vandel
Research Institute: Université de Lille,
CNRS, Inserm, CHU Lille, Institut Pasteur
de Lille
Unit/Laboratory: UMS2014 PLBS
City: Lille
Region : Hauts-de-France
Website: wikis.univ-lille.fr/bilille

Highlights:

- In 2020, bilille saw its first three permanent engineering positions dedicated to the platform.
- **Publication of miRkwood**, a software package for the discovery of microRNAs and their hairpin precursors in plant genomes. It combines multiple evidences to support the prediction: thermodynamical stability, conservation, miRNA:miRNA* duplex,... miRkwood has a user-friendly interface to navigate in the data, as well as many export options to conduct further analyses.

ACTIVITY REPORT 2019-2020

BiRD

Scientific Lead: Richard Redon
& Jérémie Bourdon
Technical Lead : Audrey Bihouée
Research Institute: Université de Nantes,
Inserm
Unit/Laboratory: UMR1087/LS2N
City: Nantes
Region : Pays de la Loire
Website: pf-bird.univ-nantes.fr

Highlights:

- BiRD co-organized the 19th edition of JOBIM in July 2019, jointly proposed by the Société Française de Bioinformatique (SFBI), the Institut Français de Bioinformatique (IFB) and the GdR Bioinformatique Moléculaire (GDR BIM). This edition of JOBIM in Nantes brought together up to 473 researchers and engineers. The program was composed of 7 keynote speakers, 28 oral presentations selected by a national scientific committee, 212 posters and 16 demonstrations. Five thematic sessions were organized, bringing together experts in their fields.
- MUDIS4LS
- An article, in collaboration with LS2N and LAMSADE computer science research units, on the FAIRification of scientific data through the **exploitation of provenance traces in workflows** was published in [Semantic Web Journal](#).
- BiRD provided computing and storage resources for a GWAS project on **intracranial aneurysms published in Nature Genetics**
- BiRD is hosting Sofia Strubbia, engineer and leader of the Biogenouest federative project «MoDal». This project aims to break down the barriers between life science fields by integrating multi-scale data and promoting the interoperability of data and analysis tools.

CBiB

Scientific Lead: Macha Nikolski
Technical Lead : Alexis Groppi
Research Institute: Université de Bordeaux
Unit/Laboratory: Centre de Bioinformatique
de Bordeaux
City: Bordeaux
Region : Nouvelle-Aquitaine
Website: cbib.u-bordeaux.fr

Highlights:

- **MAGITICS: Machine learning for diGital diagnosTICS of antimicrobial resistance.**
The international MAGITICS project is developing new machine learning approaches to model antibiotic resistance in order to be able to give a faster diagnosis, to have better surveillance, and to predict the emergence of resistance. Specifically, our machine learning models aim to guide treatment selection by assessing the level of resistance, provide targets for the generation of new antibiotics, and assist in the surveillance of antibiotic resistance in the patient population (human and animal around the world). To achieve this, we have assembled a transnational team (Canada, China, Finland, France) with international experts in antibiotic resistance and with demonstrated expertise in machine learning applied to both genomics and metabolomics. Our transnational team has all the elements to have a strong impact and continue to collaborate well after the JPIAMR funding period.
- **INEXTVIR: EU MSCA ITN project: «Innovative Network for Next Generation Training and Sequencing of Virome».** INEXTVIR is a European Marie-Curie training network of Belgium, of 15 laboratories in France, Spain, Belgium, Slovenia and the United Kingdom. This project is interested in plant viruses which are responsible for 50% of emerging diseases in the world and are a major threat to many agricultural crops. INEXTVIR seeks to provide a better understanding of viral communities and their role in agricultural ecosystems using the latest advances in high-throughput sequencing (HTS) technologies coupled with modern Big Data analytical approaches and socio-economic analysis. In this project the CBiB is developing artificial intelligence approaches for the identification of viruses in complex samples.

HIGHLIGHTS ON IFB PLATFORMS

GenotoulBioinfo

Scientific Lead: Christine Gaspin
Technical Lead: Christophe Klopp
Research Institute: INRAE
Unit/Laboratory: MIAT 0875
City: Toulouse
Region: Occitanie
Website: bioinfo.genotoul.fr

Highlights:

- New training on nextflow workflows: [How to run a nf-core nextflow workflow on genotoul ?](#)
- Between 2015 and 2020, the Genotoul Bioinfo platform was a partner of the ANR 'Jeunes Chercheurs' project Aeschynod directed by Jean-François Arrighi from CIRAD. Philippe Leleu and Léo Lamy, short-term contractors, performed most of the bioinformatics analysis of the project, supervised by Christophe Klopp. They assembled and annotated the genome, built the annotation database, and performed bioinformatics analyzes to find metabolic nitrogen fixation pathways in *Aeschynomene evenia*. [Quilbé, J., Lamy, L., Brottier, L. et al. Genetics of nodulation in *Aeschynomene evenia* uncovers mechanisms of the rhizobium – legume symbiosis. *Nat Commun* 12, 829 (2021), [DOI.org/10.1038/s41467-021-21094-7](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-21094-7)

GenOuest

Scientific Lead: Jacques Nicolas
Technical Lead : Olivier Collin
Research Institute: CNRS
Unit/Laboratory: UMR6074
City: Rennes
Region : Bretagne
Website: genouest.org
cesgo.org

Highlights:

- The two last years confirmed the involvement of GenOuest in the field of scientific data management. This is demonstrated by the participation in two projects. The first is the co-lead of the maDMP4LS (machine actionable Data Management Plan for Life Sciences) project funded by ANR (ANR-19-DATA-0017-01). The purpose of this 18 months project is to use the Data Management for the automated configuration of IFB computing resources (storage space requirements, accounts, data access). The second project is ELIXIR-CONVERGE, aiming at the standardization of life science data management across Europe. GenOuest is involved in the WP3 that elaborated the [RDMkit](#).

HIGHLIGHTS ON IFB PLATFORMS

iCONICS

Scientific Lead: Stanley Durreleman
Technical Lead: Lars Jorgensen
Research Institute: ICM
Unit/Laboratory: UMR7225/UMRS1127
City: Paris
Region : Ile-de-France
Website: iconics.institutducerveau-icm.org

Highlights:

- **IntegrParkinson pilot project.** Development of a pilot project in the framework of action A2.1, with FLI, France Génomique and MetaboHub: «Development of an interactive software for the analysis of integrated multimodal datasets in the study of Parkinson's disease and in two use-cases in radiomique.»
- **Involvement in the IFB.** Important participation in several IFB actions: helpdesk, call for challenges, health WG, management college.
- **DRAGEN.** Utilizing the Illumina DRAGEN platform to provide rapid turnaround of results.
- **New name in 2021.** Paris Brain Institute's Data Analysis Core

IFB-Core

Scientific Lead: Claudine Médigue
& Jacques van Helden
Research Institute: CNRS
Unit/Laboratory: UMR3601
City: Evry
Region: Ile-de-France
Website: france-bioinformatique.fr

Highlights:

- **MUDIS4LS.** Secured euros 16.5M of funding for the next five years by the French Ministry of Higher Education, Research and Innovation under the Mutualised Digital Spaces for FAIR Life Sciences roadmap.
- **Task force <IFB vs COVID-19>.** IFB provides a collection of bioinformatics resources (software, databases, analysis results, publications, training material,...) to address the COVID-19 health crisis and to provide support to the teams directly involved in the fight against the virus.
- **CNRS crystal medal for IFB members.** Group Crystal Medal 2020 - **Christophe Blanchet**, Crystal Medal 2020 - **Vincent Lefort** and Crystal Medal 2020 - **Alexandra Louis**
- **IFB/ELIXIR-FR Newsletter.** Since June 2020, the IFB has set up a newsletter for its members and user communities. Each month, the newsletter brings together important information from IFB, ELIXIR and European initiatives, as well as international events, job vacancies, training & outreach, and scientific publications.
- **Biolmage Informatics Index (Biini)** resource became an ELIXIR Recommend Interoperability Resource.
- Together with ELIXIR-CH and the **ELIXIR human Copy Number Variation Community**, coordinated the **publication** of the Community roadmap. The IFB/ELIXIR-FR also became **co-coordinator of the ELIXIR Tools platform**.
- Helped create the **FAIR-compliant ecosystems of tools and resources**.
- Extended the ELIXIR France Service Delivery Plan with a joint submission with the ELIXIR Norwegian Node for EDAM.
- **Co-organized**, with ELIXIR-LU, a **capacity building workshop** on "ELIXIR Best practices in research data management and stewardship".

Institut Curie

Scientific Lead: Emmanuel Barillot
Technical Lead: Philippe Hupé
& Nicolas Servant
Research Institute: Institut Curie
Unit/Laboratory: U900 Inserm
City: Paris
Region: Ile-de-France
Website: bioinfo-pf-curie.github.io
science.curie.fr/plateformes/bioinformatique

Highlights:

- Research analysis pipelines redesigned in Nextflow and made **available to the community**. To date, the RNA-seq, ATAC-seq, ChIP-seq, Hi-C, raw-QC analysis pipelines and specific allele have been deployed.
- In order to harmonize practices between different developers and bioinformaticians, we have defined the procedures for the development cycle of bioinformatics pipelines ([Kamoun et al., 2021](#)), **the details of which are available**. The image below illustrates the git branching model used by biogitflow.

MBI

Scientific Lead: Marie-Dominique Devignes
Technical Lead : Jonathan Alcuta
Research Institute: CNRS INS2I, Inria,
Université de Lorraine
Unit/Laboratory: LORIA, UMR7503
City: Nancy
Region : Grand Est
Website: mbi.loria.fr

Highlights:

- **On-line tutorials** have been organized by Isaure Chauvot de Beauchene on the MBI-DS4H platform in 2019 and 2020: (1) hands-on tutorial about RNA-protein docking, at the Winter School AlgoSB, 14-18 january 2019, in Marseille, (2) hands-on tutorial for the 3D modeling of nucleic acid – protein complexes, using the ATTRACT docking software, April-May 2020.
- In 2020, local competencies in Data Science for Health have joined the MBI platform, which becomes **MBI-DS4H : Modelling Biomolecules and their Interactions – Data Science for Health**

HIGHLIGHTS ON IFB PLATFORMS

MICROSCOPE

Scientific Lead: Claudine Médigue
& David Vallenet
Technical Lead: Mathieu Dubois
Research Institute: CEA
Unit/Laboratory: UMR8030
City: Evry
Region: Ile-de-France
Website: mage.genoscope.cns.fr/microscope

Highlights:

- **Publication of a new paper presenting the MicroScope platform** in the 2020 Database issue of [Nucleic Acids Research Journal](#). This paper focuses on some major improvements since 2017:
 - improvements of the genome browser and of the sequence/organism selector,
 - update of the automatic annotation procedure,
 - new tools for functional annotation of genes (eggNOG, essential genes, prediction of resistome and virulome),
 - new tools for the characterization of genomic regions (antiSMASH 5, Integron Finder, MacSyFinder and CRISPRCas Finder),
 - ongoing work on new functionalities dedicated to pangenomics, MicroScope Genome Clusters and pangenome computation and identification of Regions of genomic plasticity with the PanRGP tool.
- **Development of bioinformatics methods for the analysis of microbial pangenomes:**
 - **PPanGGOLiN** builds pangenomes through a graphical model and a statistical method to partition gene families in persistent, shell and cloud genomes. It integrates both information on protein-coding genes and their genomic neighborhood to build a graph of gene families where each node is a gene family and each edge is a relation of genetic contiguity
 - **panRGP** predicts Regions of Genome Plasticity (RGPs) that are clusters of genes made of shell and cloud genomes in the pangenome graph. Most of them arise from Horizontal gene transfer (HGT) and correspond to Genomic Islands (GIs). RGPs from different genomes are next grouped in spots of insertion based on their conserved flanking persistent genes.

MIGALE

Scientific Lead: Sophie Schbath
Technical Lead: Valentin Loux
Research Institute: INRAE
Unit/Laboratory: UR 1404
City: Jouy-en-Josas
Region: Ile-de-France
Website: migale.inrae.fr

Highlights:

- Development, in collaboration with EDYP (PROFI) of **ProteoRE** (Proteomics Research Environment) aiming at centrally providing the proteomics community with an online research service enabling biologists/clinicians without programming expertise to perform the functional analysis and to interpret their proteomics data through the Web.
- Continuation of the **bioinformatics training cycle** through practice. Creation of two new modules: "comparative bacterial genomics" and "shotgun metagenomic data analysis" (2 days).
- **Florilege**, a knowledge base about microbial habitat, phenotypes and uses. Florilege combines the information computed by advanced text-mining of the scientific literature and information from Biological Resource Centers. Information retrieval is supported by a powerful semantic search engine that enables ontology-based query.
- **Easy16S** : User-friendly interface to explore metabarcoding data.
- Bioinformatics and biostatistics analysis of the major France-Genomics sequencing **project MetaPDO-Cheese**: analysis of the microbial diversity maintained by the family of 44 French AOP cheeses.

MMG-GBIT

Scientific Lead: Christophe Bérout
 Technical Lead: David Salgado
 Research Institute: Inserm
 Unit/Laboratory: U 1251
 City: Marseille
 Region : PACA
 Website: geneticsandbioinformatics.eu

Highlights:

- **Development of the GOLD platform** from the Inserm Genomic Variability 2018 Cross-Cutting Program to study Human Genome Variability.
- Participation in the European Joint Programme for Rare Diseases (EJP-RD). **Creation of the DOLPHIN system** to identify key residues of protein domains and revisit variant classification through PM1 and BS1/PM2 evidence.
- Leader of the ELIXIR hCNV Community.
- Participation to the FUSAFE2 international project to identify molecular signatures predictive of the adverse effects after 5-FU treatment.
- **Development of the RDVD database** to store and analyse genomic data which was instrumental for the creation of the GOLD and SoVAD Platforms.
- **Development of BANCCO**, the national database for CNV.
- Strong involvement in national (digital mutualized spaces for health data) and international genomic sharing initiatives (B1MG), Saunders G, et al. Nat Rev Genet. 2019 Nov;20(11):693-701.
[DOI: 10.1038/s41576-019-0156-9](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41576-019-0156-9).
- Several publications from collaborative studies:
 - Gargaun E et al. Biomedicines. 2021 Feb 20;9(2):219.
[DOI:10.3390/biomedicines9020219](https://doi.org/10.3390/biomedicines9020219);
 - Stefanovic S et al. Elife. 2020 Aug 17;9:e55124
[DOI: 10.7554/eLife.55124](https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.55124);
 - Barthélémy I, et al. Skelet Muscle. 2020 Aug 7;10(1):23.
[DOI: 10.1186/s13395-020-00239-0](https://doi.org/10.1186/s13395-020-00239-0);
 - Milleron O. et al. J Am Coll Cardiol. 2020 Mar 3;75(8):843-853.
[DOI: 10.1016/j.jacc.2019.12.043](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jacc.2019.12.043);
 - J Melendez. et al. Nat Commun 12, 749 (2021).
[DOI.org/10.1038/s41467-020-20290-1](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-020-20290-1);
[DOI: 10.1016/j.jacc.2019.12.043](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jacc.2019.12.043);
 - O Serralbo et al. elife 2020;9:e56312
[DOI: 10.7554/eLife.56312](https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.56312)

ORPHANET

Scientific Lead: Ana Rath
 Technical Lead : Marc Hanauer
 Research Institute: Inserm
 Unit/Laboratory: US14
 City: Paris
 Region : Ile-de-France
 Website: orpha.net/consor/cgi-bin/index.php

Highlights:

- 45 million pages of orpha.net viewed in 2020. Around 1,7 million visitors per month from 236 countries.
- Metrics Bioschemas Orphanet: 10542 Clinical entities pages with markups, 9 languages, 94878 pages with Bioschemas 'Markups Disease profile: Label, synonym, Definition, Unique ORPHAcode, Prevalence, Mappings to nomenclatures (ICD, OMIM, UMLS, GARD...).
- Orphadata was formally designated as an ELIXIR Core Data Resource at the start of 2019. Orphadata was added to this list after a detailed study conducted by an independent panel of reviewers following Orphanet's decision to adopt a more open licence, compatible with Open Science principles (Creative Commons BY-4.0).
- An article co-authored by Orphanet, Orphanet Ireland and EURORDIS, presents an analysis of the prevalence data in the Orphanet database and estimates that the number of people living with rare diseases between 263–446 million people in the world. [Estimating cumulative point prevalence of rare diseases: analysis of the Orphanet database.](#)
- **RD-CODE** co-funded by the Third Health Programme, started on January 2019 and ended in December 2020. The objective of this project is to support Member States in improving gathering information on rare diseases by implementation of ORPHA codes. To facilitate IT access to nomenclature data and allow flexible implementation across Europe and fields, an API (Application Programming Interface) is now provided. An [Orphanet Data visualisation tool](#) has been developed, allowing users to search for the clinical entities (groups of disorders, disorders, sub-types) that are present in the Orphanet nomenclature pack in all the API languages. Orphadata now also provides a complete [Orphanet Nomenclature Pack](#) for coding purposes in 9 languages. These files provide the computable information necessary to achieve the implementation of ORPHAcodes in Health Information Systems, and ensure easier and accurate coding.
- The European Joint Programme on Rare Diseases ([EJP RD](#)) brings over 130 institutions from 35 countries: to create a comprehensive, sustainable ecosystem allowing a virtuous circle between research, care and medical innovation to improve the impact, reuse and funding of RD research. Orphanet as a network is a partner, and co-leads the Pillar 2 of the EJP. Orphanet will develop its collection of research data and resources, and provide training on the Orphanet nomenclature and ORDO. A « train the trainers » training session was held in 2020 to prepare national training sessions, to be led by Orphanet national teams. The first version of a web-based RD research analysis platform open to Orphanet partners and IRDIRC funders was made available.

PACA-Bioinfo

Scientific Lead: Matthieu Legendre
Technical Lead: Sébastien Santini
Research Institute: CNRS
Unit/Laboratory: UMR7256
City: Marseille
Region : PACA
Website: igs.cnrs-mrs.fr/paca-bioinfo

Highlights:

- Poirot O, Jeudy S, Abergel C, Claverie JM. A Puzzling Anomaly in the 4-Mer Composition of the Giant Pandoravirus Genomes Reveals a Stringent New Evolutionary Selection Process. *J Virol.* 2019 Nov 13;93(23):e01206-19.
[DOI: 10.1128/JVI.01206-19](https://doi.org/10.1128/JVI.01206-19). [PMID: 31534042](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31534042/);
[PMCID: PMC6854483](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/PMC6854483/).
All calculations were carried out on the platform.
- Jeudy S, Bertaux L, Alempic JM, Lartigue A, Legendre M, Belmudes L, Santini S, Philippe N, Beucher L, Biondi EG, Juul S, Turner DJ, Couté Y, Claverie JM, Abergel C. Exploration of the propagation of transpovirons within Mimiviridae reveals a unique example of commensalism in the viral world. *ISME J.* 2020 Mar;14(3):727-739.
[DOI: 10.1038/s41396-019-0565-y](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41396-019-0565-y).
Epub 2019 Dec 10. PMID: 31822788; PMCID: PMC7031253.
The assembly and annotation of the different genomes was carried out on the platform.
- Jeudy S, Rigou S, Alempic JM, Claverie JM, Abergel C, Legendre M. The DNA methylation landscape of giant viruses. *Nat Commun.* 2020 May 27;11(1):2657.
[DOI: 10.1038/s41467-020-16414-2](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-020-16414-2).
PMID: 32461636; PMCID: PMC7253447.
The assembly, analysis of SMRT-seq data and annotation of the different genomes were carried out on the platform.

Pasteur Hub

Scientific Lead: Marie Agnès Dillies
(formerly Olivier Gascuel)
Technical Lead: Christophe Malabat
Research Institute: Institut Pasteur
Unit/Laboratory: Hub de Bioinformatique et Biostatistique
City: Paris
Region : Ile-de-France
Website: research.pasteur.fr/en/team/bioinformatics-and-biostatistics-hub

Highlights:

- **Bioinformatics program for PhD students.**
Compulsory course for all students starting a PhD thesis at the Institut Pasteur. This course provides basic training in R, statistics and data analysis to all PhD students at the Institute. Optional training in Bioinformatics and Image Analysis is also offered. 70 PhD students are trained each year.
- **Diversification of giant and large eukaryotic dsDNA viruses predated the origin of modern eukaryotes.**
Phylogenetic analysis of giant virus proteins led to the conclusion that these viruses are probably the origin of RNA polymerase in proto-eukaryotes.
[10.1073/pnas.1912006116](https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1912006116)
- Participation in the **curation of SARS-CoV-2 data in the GISAID database.** A dedicated optimal alignment tool has been developed and is available.
[DOI.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btaa871](https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btaa871).

PlantBioinfoPF

Scientific Lead: Hadi Quesneville
Technical Lead : Michael Alaux
Research Institute: INRAE
Unit/Laboratory: UR1164
City: Versailles
Region : Ile-de-France
Website: urgi.versailles.inrae.fr/Platform

Highlights:

- **Integrative Bioinformatics 2019 conference** organization.
- New major version of the REPET tool: **REPET v3** including docker container.
- Start of the **BioinfOmics Research Infrastructure** together with GenetoulBioinfo, Sigenae and MIGALE.
- Set-up of our Cloud OpenStack Infrastructure (1760 vCPU, 4.4 TB RAM, 130 TB Ceph HDD storage).

PRABI-AMSB

Scientific Lead: Vincent Navratil
Technical Lead: Dominique Guyot
Training Lead: Christine Oger
Research Institute: Université de Lyon
Unit/Laboratory: FR3728 BioEEnvis
City: Lyon
Region: Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes
Website: amsb.prabi.fr

Highlights:

- **Bioinformatics support to COVID-19 projects (IFB task force, HCL data analysis support, EVBC collaboration, SARS-CoV-2 interaction data biocuration, VirHostNet 2.0 SARS-CoV-2 release.** Implementation of a special COVID-19 version, SARS-CoV-2, implementation of a pipeline for the analysis of Rna-seq data from COVID-19 patients. In-silico prediction of virus/host protein-protein interactions. Scoring of protein-protein interactions in collaboration with SIB and Pasteur Institute. Phylogenetic analysis of SARS-CoV-2 Envelope protein.
- Bioinformatics support to the FR BioEEnvis members in the environment, biodiversity and one-health thematic fields.
- Bioinformatics Training (Linux, R, computing resources)
 - **Influenza virus infection induces widespread alterations of host cell splicing.** Usama Ashraf, Clara Benoit-Pilven, Vincent Navratil, Cécile Ligneau, Guillaume Fournier, Sandie Munier, Odile Sismeiro, Jean-Yves Coppée, Vincent Lacroix, and Nadia Naffakh. 2020, **NAR Genomics and Bioinformatics**. DOI: [10.1093/nargab/lqaa095](https://doi.org/10.1093/nargab/lqaa095).
 - **Comparison of Nucleic Acid Extraction Methods for a Viral Metagenomics Analysis of Respiratory Viruses.** Marina Sabatier, Antonin Bal, Grégory Destras, Hadrien Regue, Grégory Quéromès, Valérie Cheynet, Bruno Lina, Claire Bardel, Karen Bregel-Pesce, Vincent Navratil, and Laurence Josset. 2020, **Microorganisms**. DOI: [10.3390/microorganisms8101539](https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms8101539).
 - **The wild grape genome sequence provides insights into the transition from dioecy to hermaphroditism during grape domestication.** Hélène Badouin, Amandine Velt, François Gindraud, Timothée Flutre, Vincent Dumas, Sonia Vautrin, William Marande, Jonathan Corbi, Erika Sallet, Jérémy Ganofsky, Sylvain Santoni, Dominique Guyot, Eugenia Ricciardelli, Kristen Jepsen, Jos Käfer, Hélène Berges, Eric Duchêne, Franck Picard, Philippe Huguency, Raquel Tavares, Roberto Bacilieri, Camille Rustenholz, and Gabriel A.B. Marais. 2020, **Genome biology**. DOI: [10.1186/s13059-020-02131-y](https://doi.org/10.1186/s13059-020-02131-y).
 - **Advances in Analyzing Virus-Induced Alterations of Host Cell Splicing.** Usama Ashraf, Clara Benoit-Pilven, Vincent Lacroix, Vincent Navratil, and Nadia Naffakh. 2019, **Trends in Microbiology**. DOI: [10.1016/j.tim.2018.11.004](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tim.2018.11.004)

South Green

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Highlights:

• **Development of bioinformatics pipelines to support NGS analyses in Plants.** Since 2019, a pipeline called **CulebrONT** has been developed as an open-source, scalable, modular and traceable Snakemake pipeline, able to launch multiple assembly tools in parallel. Besides, as a result of the Genome Harvest project, pipelines for analyses of large structural variation in banana (VCFHunter) and produce phylogenomic karyotypes in citrus (TraceAncestor) were published and made available as Galaxy workflows in the South Green instances.

1. Baurens, F.-C., Martin, G., Hervouet, C., Salmon, F., Yohomé, D., Ricci, S., Rouard, M., Habas, R., Lemainque, A., Yahiaoui, N., et al. (2019). Recombination and Large Structural Variations Shape Interspecific Edible Bananas Genomes. *Mol Biol Evol* 36, 97–111. [DOI.org/10.1093/molbev/msy199](https://doi.org/10.1093/molbev/msy199).

2. Ahmed, D., Comte, A., Curk, F., Costantino, G., Luro, F., Dereeper, A., Mournet, P., Froelcher, Y., and Ollitrault, P. (2019). Genotyping by sequencing can reveal the complex mosaic genomes in gene pools resulting from reticulate evolution: a case study in diploid and polyploid citrus. *Annals of Botany* 123, 1231–1251. [DOI.org/10.1093/aob/mcz029](https://doi.org/10.1093/aob/mcz029).

• **Curation and evolution of Plant genomic databases.** In 2020, some focus has been made on a subset of information systems supported by the platform. It included:
- the release and **publication of GreenPhylDB v5** which introduces the concept of comparative pangenomics by harnessing multiple genome sequences by species. In total, 46 plant species were considered to build gene families and predict their homologous relationships through phylogenetic-based analyses. **GreenPhyl**
- the release of a new version of one of the South Green Genome Hubs dedicated to the Banana genomics which got a facelift with new genomes and tools to explore them. **Banana genom hub**.

• The South Green Genome Hubs were advertised during the virtual **JOBIM 2020 for which South Green was co-organizer of the event.**

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Highlights:

Whereas the platform is involved in protein structure analysis and modeling, including recent efforts on protein loop modeling, latest developments have focused on protein-protein interactions. This research involved annotation of interactomics data and Protein complex modeling and resulted in several publications.

• **DaReUS-Loop: a web server to model multiple loops in homology models.** Karami Y; Rey J; Postic G; Murail S; Tufféry P; de Vries SJ, *Nucleic Acids Res.* 2019 Jul 2;47(W1):W423-W428.

• **Probing Protein Interaction Networks by Combining MS-Based Proteomics and Structural Data Integration.** Postic G; Marcoux J; Reys V; Andreani J; Vandembrouck Y; Bousquet MP; Mouton-Barbosa E; Cianféran S; Burlet-Schiltz O; Guerois R; Labesse G; Tufféry P. *J Proteome Res.* 2020 Jul 2;19(7):2807-2820.

TAGC

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Highlights:

- **Remap 2020.** ReMap is an integrative analysis of Homo sapiens and Arabidopsis thaliana transcriptional regulators from DNA-binding experiments such as ChIP-seq, ChIP-exo, DAP-seq from public sources (GEO, ENCODE, ENA). The ReMap human atlas consists of 165 million (M) peaks from 1,135 transcription factors (TFs), transcription coactivators (TCAs) and chromatin-remodeling factors (CRFs). The ReMap Arabidopsis regulatory atlas consists of 2.6M peaks from 372 transcriptional regulators. We also provide a catalog of 33 histone modifications and variants across 4.5M peaks. All catalogs are available to browse or download either for a given TF or biotype (cell line, tissue), or for the entire dataset.
Publication: [ReMap 2020: a database of regulatory regions from an integrative analysis of Human and Arabidopsis DNA-binding sequencing experiments.](#); DOI: [10.1093/nar/gkz945](https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkz945).
PMID: 31665499.
- **MoonDB 2.0** is a database of predicted (through the analysis of protein-protein interaction networks and functional annotations) and manually curated extreme multifunctional (EMF) and moonlighting proteins, i.e. proteins that perform multiple unrelated functions. MoonDB 2.0 contains a set of human 238 EMFs and 54 EMFs from mouse, fly, worm and yeast. In addition to novel predictions, this update contains 63 human and yeast proteins that were manually curated from literature, including descriptions of moonlighting functions and associated references. MoonDB's interface was fully redesigned and improved, and its entries are now cross-referenced in the UniProt Knowledgebase (UniProtKB).
Publication: [MoonDB 2.0: an updated database of extreme multifunctional and moonlighting proteins](#); DOI: [10.1093/nar/gky1039](https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gky1039).
PMID: 30371819.
- **Ologram** is a tool to determine the significance of total overlap length between genomic regions sets. Indeed, various bioinformatics analyses provide sets of genomic coordinates of interest. Whether two such sets possess a functional relation is a frequent question. This is often determined by interpreting the statistical significance of their overlaps. However, only few existing methods consider the lengths of the overlap, and they do not provide a resolutive p-value. Here, we introduce OLOGRAM, which performs overlap statistics between sets of genomic regions described in BEDs or GTF. It uses Monte Carlo simulation, taking into account both the distributions of region and inter-region lengths, to fit a negative binomial model of the total overlap length.
Publication: [OLOGRAM: Determining significance of total overlap length between genomic regions sets](#); DOI: [10.1093/bioinformatics/btz810](https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btz810).
PMID: 31688931.

HIGHLIGHTS ON IFB PLATFORMS

ACTIVITY REPORT 2019-2020

IFB PLATFORMS NETWORK EVOLUTION

INSTITUT FRANÇAIS DE
BIOINFORMATIQUE

In 2020, IFB launched a call for three modalities of adhesion: member platform, contributing platform or associated team.

Since its foundation in 2013, the IFB's network of platforms and teams has expanded. This enlargement also involved a diversification of the respective contributions of the federated platforms to the national infrastructure: hosting of user accounts on computing facilities, software development and deployment, database development, consulting and support to biologists for the analysis of their data, and training.

In 2020, IFB launched a call for the renewal of its teams, which led in February to an update of the regional coverage. This renewal call defines three modalities of contribution to the IFB's national service infrastructure:

1. Member platforms are teams active at three categories of IFB's missions (services, training, and innovative developments), and engaged in a quality management system (QMS, with ISO9001 and/or NFX50 labels). Member platforms take part in the full-cost model of IFB and contribute to the national bioinformatics key performance indicators.

2. Contributing platforms are teams whose activities are essentially oriented towards services in at least one of the three above-mentioned categories, without requiring to develop a full-cost model or be engaged in a quality management system.

3. Associated teams are teams whose activities are primarily oriented towards research, but who specifically contribute to the deployment of services, training and/or innovative developments of IFB.

The three different levels of contribution allow the affiliated bioinformatics platforms and teams to benefit from the IFB dynamics and its European integration via the ELIXIR infrastructure. Indeed, they are embarked in grant applications for mutualized projects (e.g. the PIA3 ESR/Equipex+ MUDIS4LS project), in international projects, and they can deploy their bioinformatics resources (tools, databases, etc) on IFB national computing resources (core cluster and cloud).

The applications for membership were evaluated based on a duly motivated engagement letter, that included a summary of key performance indicators for the different types of activities and contributions. In total, **the 2020 call led to the adhesion of 21 member platforms, 8 contributing platforms and 7 associated teams, validated by the IFB Board of Directors.**

The new list of partner affiliated bioinformatics platforms is available on the [IFB website](#). This update of the IFB network of bioinformatics platforms will undoubtedly contribute to shaping the landscape of the services deployed by IFB in the forthcoming years.

GOING FORWARD 2021-2025: UPCOMING PROJECTS

MUDIS4LS paves the 2021-2025 roadmap

EMERGEN PROJECT:

CONSORTIUM FOR THE SURVEILLANCE AND
RESEARCH ON EMERGENT PATHOGENS VIA MICROBIAL

GENomicsABROMICS PROJECT :

A NUMERICAL PLATFORM ON ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE
(ABR) TO STORE, INTEGRATE, ANALYZE AND SHARE MULTI-OMICS
DATA

PROJECTS IN **AGRONOMY AND ENVIRONMENT**

PROJECTS IN **MARINE BIODIVERSITY**

Introduction to the 2021-2025 IFB roadmap

The IFB 2018-2021 roadmap initiated a deep restructuring of IFB services, training and innovative developments relying on a collective organization of the work packages and actions, operated by mutualized task forces composed of volunteers from all IFB platforms (see our 2017-2018 activity report,

[DOI:10.5281/zenodo.3898660](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3898660)).

Following the final evaluation of the national research infrastructures, the ANR and the Ministry of Research decided to grant IFB a supplementary 2.8M euros funding for functioning and temporary staff, and our supporting research organisms (CNRS, INRAE, CEA, and Inserm) committed to open seven permanent positions to ensure the sustainability of the bioinformatics infrastructure.

Our SAB, however, warned us about the foreseeable future expansion of the needs of our target communities for compute and storage infrastructure, as well as human support.

Quite timely, in February 2020, the French Ministry of Research launched a funding call (PIA3 ESR/Equipex+, for Programme d'Investissements d'Avenir Équipements Structurants pour la recherche) for a rationalization of the equipment. The call targeted multi-site projects including a strong dimension of mutualization.

It was granted with a total budget of 333 M euros, including 90 M euros targeted to deploy digital infrastructures, with a condition to install the new equipment in data centers labeled at the national or regional levels.

MUDIS4LS paves the 2021-2025 roadmap

IFB led an ambitious application entitled **Mutualised Digital Spaces for Life Sciences (MUDIS4LS)**, with a consortium of 37 teams from 16 research organisms and universities, bringing together 137 persons involved for part or full-time, totaling 3000 person/months of human resources. This project was granted with a **16.5M euros budget by the French government**, and IFB supporting research institutions committed to open additional permanent positions to ensure the sustainability of the infrastructure. Beyond the financial and human resources provided by MUDIS4LS, we realized that its structuring virtues are already effective even before its start. This project will pave the way of the IFB 2021-2025 road map, by federating our 21 member platforms around the organization of compute, storage and software services.

A strong axis of MUDIS4LS is the life-long orchestration of data fluxes generated by research projects, from the data sources (in collaboration with the data-producing national infrastructures) to the deposition in international repositories (data brokering). The MUDIS4LS project generalized the maDMP approach in order to apply it to each step of the data life cycle. The data management plan will thus enable to trigger transfers and monitor the evolution of the data from its production by data-producing infrastructures to its deposition in international repositories.

The planned infrastructure addresses all the deployment layers:

- hosting in 4 national and 7 regional centers;
- purchase of new servers;
- subcontracting of compute and storage capacity to regional mesocenters;
- deployment of generic and domain-specific computing and data services.

These deployments are managed through 4 technological work packages, and their effectiveness will be challenged via 5 thematic implementation studies targeting different communities of life and health sciences: marine ecology, health, microbiology, agriculture and environment.

EMERGEN PROJECT: Consortium for the surveillance and re-search on EMERgent pathogens via microbial GENomics

Within the framework of the national COVID-19 genomic surveillance project (EMERGEN), IFB is in charge of deploying a digital platform that will allow the collection of SARS-CoV-2 genomic sequences produced by about 40 sequencing facilities, analyze these sequences to detect known variants and to discover new variants, and combine the results of this variant analysis with patient data within a certified digital space for health data storage (HDS).

The **EMERGEN digital platform** will underpin both epidemiological surveillance and research activities. During the first two years, the project will be dedicated to the processing of COVID-19 data, but in the longer term it will aim at developing a generic infrastructure for the processing of data about emerging infectious diseases. The development of this platform will be carried out by a team including skills in DevOps, database and software development, data management and data analysis.

ABRomics project: A numerical platform on antimicrobial resistance (ABR) to store, integrate, analyze and share multi-omics data

Based on the software environment and the data management system developed in the context of MUDIS4LS, the **ABRomics** project aims at developing a secure One Health cross-sectorial online platform to make accessible bacterial infectious disease (meta)genomics data and their associated clinical and epidemiological metadata to a meta-network of researchers including epidemiologists, clinical microbiologists, and the broader research community.

The **ABRomics project** is led by IFB and Institut Pasteur and is formed by a consortium of 45 teams belonging to the main French research organizations. These teams bring together all the expertise required to build this platform (diversity of ABR research in clinical and fundamental fields, mathematical modeling methods and the whole range of expertise in computer science, bioinformatics, database and computer architecture). **ABRomics is funded at 2M euros for 4 years and will start in September 2021.**

Projects in agronomy and environment

The objective for the next four years is to develop activities at the European level for the Agro area beyond the ELIXIR Plant Science community and in collaboration with other national and international infrastructures in the domain or institutional working groups developing e-infrastructures.

IFB/ELIXIR-FR has already started with the co-coordination of the recently set up **ELIXIR Microbial Biotechnology community** and is also setting up an active contact person for the **emerging ELIXIR Food and Nutrition community**. The research units developing genomic approaches on domestic animals have set up links with EMBL-EBI, a central node of ELIXIR, through European Commission funded projects. This was not supported by ELIXIR activities so far and ELIXIR-FR is under discussion to identify possible supporting activities that would address gaps, contribute to the long-term sustainability of the resources developed and to their visibility.

Finally, the largest institute in the field, INRAE, has recently set up an institutional research infrastructure gathering and coordinating the activities of four of its IFB members, with trans domains activities (plant, animal, microbes). It will develop, together with the national infrastructure managing biological resources for Agriculture, **RARe**, activities aiming at supporting the management of FAIR data on holobionts (food, animals and plants) in the MUDIS4LS project.

Projects in marine biodiversity

In the field of biodiversity analysis and in the context of the national component of the **ERGA project**, ELIXIR-FR/IFB has already positioned itself to support the sequencing initiative of marine coastal organisms. A list of 28 species has been identified by the French teams for the pilot project.

IFB/ELIXIR-FR will also be involved from 2021 in the project recently funded by the ANR and carried by the infrastructure EMBRC-FR and the FR GO-SEE (Tara Ocean) around the development of augmented marine genomic observatories.

Finally, ELIXIR-FR is contributing to the **ELIXIR Biodiversity Focus Group** that will be involved in developing the ELIXIR participation to proposal submission to Horizon Europe calls on biodiversity along with the ERGA and BIOSCAN consortium.

ELIXIR-FR will also contribute in 2021 to the expansion of the Marine metagenomic community to a wider new “microbiome community” in ELIXIR. The ELIXIR microbiome community is initiated amongst researchers focusing on Marine microbiomes, and focused on promoting standards around metagenomic, metabarcoding and metatranscriptomics analysis, as well as trying to understand the gaps in existing reference databases. Since the challenges faced and developments devised by this ELIXIR community are not confined to the marine microbiome, and are broadly applicable to all other biomes, the ELIXIR microbiome community will be broadened to encompass all microbiomes.

ACTIVITY REPORT 2019- 2020

IFB Task Leaders and IFB-Core staff

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